

ANALYSIS OF STUDIES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes research on the development of environmental competence in the conditions of modern environmental education. The scientific-pedagogical foundations of ecological competence development have been studied.

Key words: culture, ecology, ecological education, reproductive, alternative, retrospective, ecological competence, competence.

INTRODUCTION. In the process of studying the ecological education system, comparing the ecological education and upbringing system in several developed countries, the innovative educational environment created in educational institutions, the modern teaching system and the high level of ecological knowledge and skills to study the factors that caused it to be at the level and to create effective methods based on the creative use of these experiences during research, to develop the environmental competence of students.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical aspects of the foundations of environmental education, the causes of environmental risks in the era of globalization, ways to eliminate them, scientific research aimed at developing some aspects of environmental competence in students Q. Abdurahimov, I. Kh. Ayubova, P. Berdanova, N. Bozorova, R. Kh. Y. Ahmadaliyev, N. Isakulova, Sh. Kamolkho'jayev, A. Malikova, M. E. Musayeva, V. Nikitin, N. O'. Nishonova, H. Norbo'tayev, T. Saparov, V. N. Sattorov, H. Togayev, E. O. It was carried out by Turdikulov, U. Turdikulov, D. Tokhliyev, A.S. Tokhtayev, A. Ergashev, Sh. Yunusova.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. It is appropriate to consider the approaches and scientific conclusions of scientists who have conducted research in these areas in order to clarify the scientific and pedagogical foundations of the development of ecological competence.

Czech scientist Y. Demek includes environmental education among political issues and categorizes its tasks in the following directions:

- 1) acquisition of knowledge, experiences, skills related to man and nature;
- 2) creating the ability to protect the environment;

3) ensuring a social attitude and collective approach to the solution of environmental problems;

4) formation of a positive belief in nature, development of ecological ethics. After all, today's educational tasks - ensuring the integration of various forms of social consciousness with ecological thinking - have become more urgent than ever.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main goal of the "Concept for the Development of Ecological Education" is the formation and development of ecological knowledge, consciousness and culture in the young generation, the effective organization of the ecological education process, as well as the promotion of ecological science in the world. consists of further improvement involving advanced innovative technologies.

Environmental competence should be formed and developed in the educational system up to higher education. In his research, Y. Ahmadaliyev commented on the importance of proper organization of extracurricular activities in environmental education in school education. on the basis of the organization of circles, students' interest in nature will increase, their attitude towards it will increase, their attitude towards it will be formed consciously, and their interest in other educational subjects will increase even more" [2], he says. Therefore, if environmental competence is formed and developed in preschool and school education, it is possible to achieve the intended goal and to a certain extent get rid of environmental problems caused by the human factor.

In her scientific research, N.Abdullayeva emphasizes that the question of the role of man in the earth's ecosystem should become a topic of attention of ecologists, philosophers, and cultural scientists in connection with the growing ecological crisis. According to his conclusions, "the world will be saved today by people who deeply understand the laws of nature, feel that man is a part of nature, and act on this basis. Human activity, without spontaneous impact on nature, must be in accordance with a purpose and develop harmoniously with it. And this depends on the level of moral-ecological consciousness and culture, which is formed in every person from childhood and continues until the end of his life" [1]. So, the main reason for the origin of the global ecological decline is not only the economic growth and increased consumer potential of humanity, but also the "poverty" of its humanistic attitude to nature. Implementation of the above-mentioned effective measures for environmental protection, elimination of a large-scale environmental threat, necessary conditions for the birth and

development of a physically healthy young generation for the population of the republic, and ecologically allows to create a clean living environment.

In the framework of G.Sherkoziyeva's research, it is emphasized that environmental protection and economical use of natural resources are considered an important environmental problem of today [8]. Kh. Nazarov to scientifically study and analyze the interrelationship of the ecological and moral environment, to identify problems and find solutions to them, to prevent negative effects of environmental threats on the development of society, people's lives and health, to improve the ecological thinking of the population emphasizes the importance of raising awareness of future dangers to the population and, by extension, to humanity as a whole.

SH. Ochilov's dissertation on the topic "Technologies for the development of environmental competence of students in interdisciplinary teaching of physics" [5] researched the structure and components of ecological competence of students in interdisciplinary teaching of physics, as well as methodological conditions for developing environmental competence of students in interdisciplinary teaching of physics. done The researcher concludes that it is necessary to develop knowledge and skills of social ecology in students, especially in the teaching of physics and biology, the importance of social-ecological knowledge is high.

In N. Mirzayeva's research, the study of the typological level of students' acceptance of knowledge and the development of ecological competence is a pedagogical-psychological problem, with the scientific-theoretical justification of the benchmarking strategy in the modern environmental education system and comparative analysis [4].

Kh. Khushvaktova tried to develop the theoretical foundations of the development of ecological worldview in students in the process of teaching the science of "Ecology and nature protection", the formation of ecological competences such as ecological awareness, ecological responsibility, ecological volition, respect for ecological values [7].

G.Salomova in her dissertation on the topic "Social-psychological characteristics of the formation of ethnocultural competence in students" [6] studies the socio-pedagogical foundations of the formation of ethno-ecological knowledge and skills, which are a component of ethnocultural competence in students.

In her research, G. Ismailova tried to improve the methods of forming and developing ecological culture in students based on modern approaches, and in

the teaching of the history of Uzbekistan, based on the characteristics of the system of classroom and non-auditory training processes that serve to form and develop ecological culture in students. develops recommendations to ensure the integration of studied concepts [3].

Another researcher, L. Abdunazarov, in his dissertation entitled "Improving the theoretical foundations of ecological education and upbringing" develops proposals and recommendations for improving the theoretical foundations of adaptation of environmental education and upbringing to modern requirements in the educational process.

At the new stage of development of the society, a certain experience is gained in the elimination of environmental problems and prevention of their negative consequences. However, the scale of tasks in the field requires a comprehensive solution to the problems of improving the ecological situation in our country and the region, and in this regard, combining the efforts of state bodies, public associations, civil society institutions, and citizens. Protecting a healthy and beautiful environment is the most important task of the state, society and every citizen.

Wasteful use of any material wealth, destruction of natural resources - underground resources, water, land, plants and animals - was considered a crime and a sin. In a narrow sense, the concept of uvol represents the sparing use of bread, water, salt, and grass, but in a broad sense, it reflects the rational use of all natural resources. Our nation has a number of historical achievements with purely ecological content. One of them is called "taganak". According to this custom, the people living in the mountains and foothills gather in early spring, open the springs in the mountains, clear the paths of the valleys from branches and mud, and cut the dry branches of the trees. Even today, the restoration, expansion, and spread of these industries play an important role in the formation of ecological culture.

It is necessary to develop ecological competence in the preservation of nature, to treat it based on high ethical standards, to form ecological and ethical responsibility, to increase students' knowledge and skills, practical experience, and worldview. Therefore, the task of increasing environmental culture and further development of the ecological education system directly goes back to the problems of ecoethics.

CONCLUSION. Today, people have become accustomed to treating nature with care, not to restore it, but to use more of its blessings. The predominance of consumer psychology, environmental violations, living only thinking about

today is destroying the ecological situation. These problems also arise from the neglect of environmental education and training. The shallow ecological consciousness of the population is due to the ineffectiveness and ineffectiveness of the ecological education system. Not everyone understands environmental problems, because most people get knowledge about ecology from the media or from what they hear around them. That is why it is necessary to systematically organize environmental knowledge and education, thereby using our historical achievements with ecological content.

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